

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON DRUG UTILISATION OF ANTITUBERCULAR DRUGS AND ITS ADHERENCE AT TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

Nishath Fathima*, Syeda Juveria Hussaini, Mumtaz Alam, Noorunnisa Begum

Dr. Mohd Faqrudin, Dr. Rafia Sultana

MESCO College of Pharmacy (Affiliated To Osmania Univeristy, Hyderabad), Mustaidpura, Karwan Road, Hyderabad.

Abstract:

Aims and Objectives: To determine whether the prescription is as per WHO standard drug regimen for Tuberculosis management and to assess the adherence of the patient's to prescribed drug regimen.

Materials and Methods: A Prospective observational study carried out in a tertiary care teaching hospital for a period of six-month. Study carried out in department of General Medicine and Outpatient Department (TB centre). Subjects of >12 yr. age groups with tubercular infection were enrolled in the study. Patients with severe comorbid conditions, pediatric patients (<12yrs), pregnant and lactating women were excluded. Data collection form (proforma), Questionnaire form for assessment of patient's knowledge and Morisky Medication adherence scale (MMAS scale) were the materials used. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS for windows.

Results: During the study period a total 100 TB patients were enrolled out of which 70% were males and 30% were females. The maximum numbers of patients were in the age group of 40-49 (middle age group). Previously diagnosed TB patients were (46%) and newly diagnosed TB patients were (54%). Patients of Pulmonary Tuberculosis were more (75%) in comparison with extra pulmonary Tuberculosis. In extra pulmonary Tuberculosis majority of patients were of pleural effusion (12%), TB Meningitis (10%), TB Spine (2%), TB Abdomen (11%) and Neuro TB (1%). Amongst all the patients, majority were given Category I regimen (81%) in which patients of PTB receiving Category I were (56%) and extra PTB were (25%) followed by category II regimen (22%) in which patients of PTB were (16%) and extra PTB were (6%). Out of 100 patients, 72 were adherent to treatment with the MMAS score >11 and patients with low adherence to treatment were 28 with 5-8 MMAS score. In Present Study, 75 patients were associated with out adverse drug event (ADE) were as 25 patients were associated with ADE. Adverse Drug Event reported were mild which includes nausea, vomiting (25%), and abdominal pain (14%). Major ADR's reported were in few patients including Hepatotoxicity, Isoniazid Neurotoxicity and Anaemia.

Conclusion: All the prescriptions were found to be as per WHO standard drug regimen for TB management. Tuberculosis was observed more in adults, predominantly males. HTN & DM was most common comorbidity in TB patients. Newly diagnosed TB cases were more than known cases. Category I drug regimen was given to 81% of patients as majority of cases collected were new cases so first CAT-I are prescribed. & Category II drug regimen was given to 22% of patients. Significant differences was observed in knowledge assessment of patients on the data collected pre & post counselling. Assessment of medication adherence is made by MMAS scale questionnaire which resulted in improvement of patient compliance.

Keywords: adherence, risk factor, DOTS Therapy, Pulmonary Tuberculosis, Extra Pulmonary Tuberculosis, MMAS (Morisky Medication Adherence Scale), ADR.

Corresponding Author*:**Nishath Fathima,**

MESCO College of Pharmacy,

Mustaidpura, Karwan Road,

Hyderabad.

nfathima52916@gmail.com

Ph.no : 9505472105

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nishath Fathima et al., *A Prospective Observational Study on Drug Utilisation of Antitubercular Drugs and Its Adherence at Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(08).

I-INTRODUCTION:

Background: The annual risk of tuberculosis in high burden countries is estimated to be 0.5-2%. During the year 2010, the number of global cases dropped down to 8.8 million which includes 3.2 million tuberculosis cases in women & 1.1 million people living with HIV. The global prevalence rate fell to 128 cases per 100,000 populations. About 5.7 million cases were notified through TB DOTS programme during 2010. Globally it is estimated that about 10 percent of MDR-TB cases have extensively drug resistant tuberculosis. [1]

The numbers of persons dying from TB during 2010 were about 1.4 million which includes 350,000 cases of TB & HIV co-infection. TB death rate has fallen by 40 percent since 1990 & the number of deaths is also declining (the target is of 50% by 2015). During 2010, about 2.1 million TB patients knew their HIV status with highest HIV testing rate of TB cases in Europe (80%) & Africa (59%).[1]

In July 2011, the revised estimated prevalence & incidence rate of all forms of TB in India were 256 & 185 cases per 100,000 populations respectively [2]. Since its inception in 1997, RNTCP has initiated about 15 million patients on treatment & 2.5 million lives were saved. The success rate since 2005 has been 85% among new smear positive cases. [3]

The annual risk of TB infection study conducted in the country in 2000-2003 shows that the national ARTI is about 1.5%. On the national scale, the high burden of TB in India is illustrated by the estimates that TB accounts for 17.6% of all deaths from communicable diseases & for 3.5% of all causes of deaths. More than 80% of burden of TB is due to premature death as measured in terms of DALYs lost. [3]

HIV increases a person's susceptibility to tuberculosis infection, & tuberculosis is one of the earliest opportunistic diseases to develop amongst persons infected with HIV. It increases morbidity & mortality in HIV infected persons. HIV is most potent risk factor for progression of TB infection to disease. In India, it is estimated that 2.4 million people are currently living with HIV. Recent country data shows that about 6% of TB patients are HIV positive. [2, 3] Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major threat to global public health, with an estimated 9.6 million new cases and 1.5 million deaths worldwide in 2014. [4]

It, is estimated that primary MDR-TB in India is around 2.1%. The drug resistance in retreatment cases is 13-17%. [5] XDR-TB infections are very difficult to treat and characterized by high mortality [6]. After tuberculosis medicines gradually began to

appear the death rates of tuberculosis patients were significantly reduced all over the world. Research indicates that with effective treatment, the 5-year death rates of tuberculosis can be decreased from 50% to 5% [7]. Thus, the WHO & various countries have referenced the results of numerous empirical studies to develop guidelines for tuberculosis treatment [6] that offer doctors standard & unified principles to follow when diagnosing & curing TB.

Prescriptions suggested in guidelines have better therapeutic effects, fewer side effects, lower costs, increased compliance. & are optimal choices in most circumstances. [8]

The regimen suggested in WHO guideline is commonly proper for the general patients group. But it is also allowed that the physicians modify the medicine on the basis of their experience. Research revealed that majority of TB patients can be cured if physicians prescribe medicines appropriately & patients take their medication by orders, however this research has been primarily restricted to investigating patient compliance. [9-14].

Standard anti-TB treatment requires patients to take a complex combination of drugs every other day, lasting for 6 months for new patients and 8 months for retreatment patients.[12] Such long-term, strict regimens is challenging for TB patients who may not adhere to their prescribed treatment due to treatment interruption or drop-out.[14]

Non-adherence may be driven by a myriad of factors that can be practical and behavioral. These factors include personal beliefs/environment, comorbidities, patient perception of drug therapy value, issues related to drug regimen complexity and side effect. Non-adherence is the most common cause of treatment failure and disease relapse, which can lead to prolonged infection, transmission, drug resistance and mortality. [15]

1.1 Definitions:

Case of tuberculosis: For the purpose of case notification, a TB case is defined as follows [16].

- (a) A patient diagnosed with atleast one sputum specimen positive for acid fast bacilli, or culture-positive for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, or RNTCP endorsed rapid diagnostic molecular test positive for tuberculosis. (Or)
- (b) A patient diagnosed clinically as a case of tuberculosis without microbiological confirmation, & initiated on anti-tuberculosis drugs.

**Figure-1 Mycobacterium tuberculosis
TUBERCULOSIS**

Adherence – Person takes appropriate drug regimen for required time.

New case – A patient with sputum positive pulmonary tuberculosis who never had treatment for tuberculosis or has taken anti-tuberculosis drugs for less than 4 weeks.

Relapse– A patient who returns smear positive having previously been treated for tuberculosis and declared cured after the completion of his treatment.

Return after default– A patient who returns sputum smear positive, after having left treatment for at least two months.

Cured– Initially smear positive patient who completed treatment and had negative smear result on at least two occasions.

1.2 Types of Tuberculosis: [17]

1. Pulmonary Tuberculosis:

- **Primary Tuberculosis Pneumonia**
- **Tuberculosis Pleurisy:** A granuloma located at the edge of the lung ruptures into the pleural space, the space between the lungs and the chest wall. Once the bacteria invade the space the amount of fluid increases dramatically and compresses the lung, causing shortness of breath (dyspnoea)

and sharp chest pain that worsens with a deep breath (pleurisy). A chest x-ray shows significant amounts of fluid.

- **Cavitary TB:** It involves the upper lobes of the lung. The bacteria cause progressive lung destruction by forming cavities, or enlarged air spaces. This type of TB occurs in reactivation disease. The upper lobes of the lung are affected because they are highly oxygenated.
 - **Miliary TB:** Miliary TB is disseminated TB. "Miliary" describes the appearance on chest x-ray of very small nodules throughout the lungs that look like millet seeds. Miliary TB can occur shortly after primary infection.
 - **Laryngeal TB:** TB can infect the larynx, or the vocal cord area.
2. **Extra-pulmonary Tuberculosis:** It occurs primarily in immunocompromised patients.
- **Lymph Node Disease:** Lymph nodes contain macrophages that capture the bacteria. Any lymph node can harbour uncontrolled replication of bacteria, causing the lymph node to become enlarged.
 - **Tuberculosis Peritonitis:** M. tuberculosis can involve the outer linings of the intestines and the linings inside the abdominal wall, producing increased fluid, as in tuberculosis pleuritis. Increased fluid leads to abdominal distention and pain.
 - **Tuberculosis Pericarditis:** The membrane surrounding the heart (the pericardium) is affected in this condition.

Figure-2 Types of extra-pulmonary TB

- **TB Meningitis:** *M. tuberculosis* can infect the meninges. This can be devastating, leading to permanent impairment and death. TB can be difficult to discern from a brain tumour because it may present as a focal mass in the brain with focal neurological signs. Headache, sleepiness, and coma are typical symptoms.
- **Osteal Tuberculosis:** Infection of any bone can occur. Spinal infection can lead to compression fractures and deformity of the back.
- **Adrenal Tuberculosis:** TB of the adrenal glands can lead to adrenal insufficiency.
- **Renal Tuberculosis**

1.3 Signs and symptoms: [18]

TB bacteria can cause symptoms such as:

1. Persistent cough of about 3 or 4 weeks duration.
2. Shortness of breath
3. Continuous fever
4. Chest pain
5. Haemoptysis
6. Head ache, neck stiffness in TB meningitis
7. Abdominal pain and Abd. Distention in Abdominal TB.

Other symptoms may include Weakness or fatigue, Weight loss, No appetite, Chills, Sweating at night.

Figure-3 Symptoms of TB

1.4 Diagnostic tools [19]

(i) **Sputum examination:** It is done by direct microscopy. It enables us to discover the epidemiologically most important cases of pulmonary tuberculosis, i.e., those excreting tubercle bacilli in their sputum.

If the symptoms persist after a course of broad-spectrum antibiotic, repeat sputum smear examination must be done for such patients. If one or more smears are positive, the patient is diagnosed as having smear-positive pulmonary TB. If none of the sputum specimen is positive, a chest X-ray is taken, and if findings of the X-ray are consistent with pulmonary TB, the patient is diagnosed as a case of

sputum-negative pulmonary TB.

Sputum smear microscopy for tubercle bacilli is positive when there are at least 10,000 organisms present per ml of sputum. The sputum smear positivity rate in TB/HIV patient depends on the degree of immune compromise.

False-positive results of sputum smear microscopy:

This may arise because of the following: red stain retained by scratches on the slide; accidental transfer of AFBs from a positive slide to a negative one; contamination of the slide or smear by environmental mycobacteria.

False negative results of sputum smear microscopy:

This may arise because of problems in collecting, processing, or interpreting sputum smears or because of administrative errors.

Light-emitting diode fluorescence microscopy (LED's) In a recent WHO evaluation, the diagnostic accuracy of LED microscopy was found to be comparable to that of conventional fluorescence microscopy and superior to that of conventional Ziehl-Neelson microscopy. It is therefore recommended that LED microscopy be phased in as an alternative to conventional Z-N light microscopy in both high & low-volume laboratories [20]

(ii) **Radiography:** chest X-rays are useful for diagnosis of smear negative pulmonary TB & TB in children. It is not routinely indicated in smear positive cases. X-rays are valuable tool for diagnosis of pleural & pericardial effusion, especially in early stages of the disease when clinical signs are minimal. It is essential in the diagnosis of miliary TB, Other indications are frequent or severe haemoptysis to exclude bronchiectasis or aspergilloma & in patients needing specific treatment for pneumothorax.

(iii) **Drug susceptibility testing:** DST provides definitive diagnosis of drug-resistant TB. Phenotypic method involves culturing *M.tuberculosis* in the presence of anti-TB drugs to detect growth (indicating drug resistance) or inhibition of growth (indicating drug susceptibility). Genotypic method targets specific molecular mutations associated with resistance against individual drugs. Indirect Phenotypic tests have been extensively validated & are currently regarded as gold standard.[20]

Molecular testing: Molecular line probe assay allow rapid detection of resistance to rifampicin (alone or in combination with isoniazid). It provides the DST result within one day.

(iv) **Skin Test :**

The **Mantoux test** is the preferred TB skin test. It uses tuberculin purified protein derivative (PPD), and unlike the Heaf or tine test, the Mantoux test is

quantitative. The standard 5-tuberculin-unit PPD dose is placed intracutaneously on the volar aspect of the forearm with a 26- or 27-gauge needle. This injection should produce a small, raised, blanched wheal. An experienced professional should read the test in 48 to 72 hours. The area of induration (the “bump”) is the important end point, not the area of redness. The CDC does not recommend the routine use of anergy panels. Aplisol and Tubersol 5-tuberculin-unit products are available commercially, but because of more predictable results, Tubersol appears to be the preferred product. The “booster effect” occurs in patients who do not respond to an initial skin test but show a positive reaction if retested about a week later. Patients with *M. tuberculosis* infection in past and some patients with past immunization with bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG) vaccine or past infection with other mycobacteria may “boost” with a second skin test. Despite BCG vaccination, one should not ignore a positive PPD result. [21]

The **QuantIFERON-TB Gold test** [21] measures the release of INF- γ in whole blood. For latently infected persons, INF- γ is released in response to in vitro stimulation by PPD, whereas no release occurs in blood samples taken from uninfected persons. This test can provide a diagnosis of latent TB infection within hours, instead of the 2 to 3 days required for the traditional PPD skin test.

1.5 Treatment:

Standard TB treatment regimen is isoniazid, rifampin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol for 2 months, followed by isoniazid and rifampin for 4 months, for a total of 6 months of treatment. If susceptibility to isoniazid, rifampin, and pyrazinamide is shown, ethambutol can be stopped at any time. Without pyrazinamide, a total of 9 months of isoniazid and rifampin treatment is required. [21].

Figure-4 Drug Regimens for Culture-Positive Pulmonary Tuberculosis

Initial Phase			Continuation Phase		
Regimen	Drugs	Interval and Doses ^c (Minimal Duration)	Regimen	Drugs	Interval and Doses ^{c,d} (Minimal Duration)
1	Isoniazid, rifampin, pyrazinamide, ethambutol	Seven days per week for 56 doses (8 wk) or 5 days/wk for 40 doses (8 wk) ^c	1a	Isoniazid/ rifampin	Seven days per week for 126 doses (18 wk) or 5 days/wk for 90 doses (18 wk) ^c
			1b	Isoniazid/ rifampin	Twice weekly for 36 doses (18 wk)
			1c ^d	Isoniazid/ rifapentine	Once weekly for 18 doses (18 wk)
2	Isoniazid, rifampin, pyrazinamide, ethambutol	Seven days per week for 14 doses (2 wk), then twice weekly for 12 doses (6 wk) or 5 days/wk for 10 doses (2 wk) ^e then twice weekly for 12 doses (6 wk)	2a	Isoniazid/ rifampin	Twice weekly for 36 doses (18 wk)
			2b ^d	Isoniazid/ rifapentine	Once weekly for 18 doses (18 wk)
3	Isoniazid, rifampin, pyrazinamide, ethambutol	Three times weekly for 24 doses (8 wk)	3a	Isoniazid/ rifampin	Three times weekly for 54 doses (18 wk)
4	Isoniazid, rifampin, ethambutol	Seven days per week for 56 doses (8 wk) or 5 days/wk for 40 doses (8 wk) ^c	4a	Isoniazid/ rifampin	Seven days per week for 217 doses (31 wk) or 5 days/wk for 155 doses (31 wk) ^e
			4b	Isoniazid/ rifampin	Twice weekly for 62 doses (31 wk)

There is no standard regimen for MDR-TB. Each patient's exposure history, Previous treatment history (including toxicity and adherence issues), and current susceptibility data. It may take several months for a patient with MDR-TB to become culture-negative because the drugs used lack the potency of isoniazid and rifampin [21]

Anti-tuberculosis drugs may be classified into two groups: bactericidal & bacteriostatic. [21]

I. Rifampicin(RMP):

Rifampin shows bactericidal activity against *M. tuberculosis* and several other mycobacterial species, including *M. bovis* and *M. kansasii*. Other nontuberculous mycobacteria, including MAC, show variable susceptibility to rifampin. Rifampin also is active against a broad array of other bacteria. Alteration of the target site on RNA polymerase, primarily through changes in the *rpoB* gene, leads to most forms of rifampin resistance. Rifampin is metabolized to 25-desacetyl-rifampin, which retains most of rifampin's activity; Rifampin generally is given at 600 mg daily or intermittently.

II. Isoniazid (INH):

It is highly specific for mycobacteria, with a MIC against *M. tuberculosis* of 0.01 to

0.25mcg/ml. Most nontuberculous mycobacteria such as *M. avium* are resistant to isoniazid, although *M. kansasii* and *Mycobacterium xenopi* are susceptible. The most common mechanisms of resistance result from mutations in the *katG* or *inhA* genes.

Transient elevations of the serum transaminases occur in 12% to 15% of patients receiving isoniazid and usually occur within the first 8 to 12 weeks of therapy. Overt hepatotoxicity, however, occurs in only 1% of cases. Isoniazid also may result in neurotoxicity, most frequently presenting as peripheral neuropathy or, in overdose, as seizures and coma. Isoniazid may inhibit the metabolism of phenytoin, carbamazepine, primidone, and warfarin.

Figure-5 Recommended Doses of First line Antituberculosis drugs for Adults [22]**III. Pyrazinamide :**

Drug	Recommended dose			
	Daily		3 times per week	
	Dose and range (mg/kg body weight)	Maximum (mg)	Dose and range (mg/kg body weight)	Daily maximum (mg)
Isoniazid	5 (4–6)	300	10 (8–12)	900
Rifampicin	10 (8–12)	600	10 (8–12)	600
Pyrazinamide	25 (20–30)	–	35 (30–40)	–
Ethambutol	15 (15–20)	–	30 (25–35)	–
Streptomycin ^a	15 (12–18)		15 (12–18)	1000

^a Patients aged over 60 years may not be able to tolerate more than 500–750 mg daily, so some guidelines recommend reduction of the dose to 10 mg/kg per day in patients in this age group (2). Patients weighing less than 50 kg may not tolerate doses above 500–750 mg daily (*WHO Model Formulary 2008*, www.who.int/selection_medicines/list/en/).

Adding pyrazinamide to the first 2 months of treatment with isoniazid and rifampin shortens the duration to 6 months for most patients. The most common toxicities of pyrazinamide are gastrointestinal distress, arthralgias, and elevations in the serum uric acid concentrations. Hepatotoxicity is the major limiting adverse effect and is dose-related when pyrazinamide is given daily.

IV. Ethambutol :

Ethambutol replaced p-amino salicylic acid as a first-line agent in the 1960s because it was better tolerated by patients. Ethambutol is bacteriostatic & is used in combination to prevent emergence of resistance to other drugs. In patients with renal failure, the ethambutol dose should be reduced to three times per week. Retro bulbar neuritis is the major adverse effect.

V. Thiacetazone :

Skin reactions, including rash and Stevens-Johnson's syndrome, may occur. Thiacetazone must be discontinued permanently as soon as a rash appears. Similar to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, the incidence of skin reactions is much higher in AIDS patients.

Second line Agents**VI. Streptomycin :**

Streptomycin is one of three aminoglycoside antibiotics (along with amikacin and kanamycin)

that are active against mycobacteria. It is labelled only for intramuscular dosing, streptomycin can be given safely as intravenous infusions (100 mL of dextrose 5% water or normal saline) over 30 minutes, similar to the other aminoglycosides. Streptomycin occasionally causes nephrotoxicity, although it tends to be mild and reversible. It also is capable of causing ototoxicity (vestibular and cochlear).

VII. Fluoroquinolones :

Levofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, and moxifloxacin are sometimes used to treat MDR-TB. Fluoroquinolones are useful in treating infections resistant to standard drugs & in cases with relapse.

VIII. Cycloserine :

Drug is mainly bacteriostatic. Cycloserine can produce dose-related CNS toxicity, including lethargy, confusion, or unusual behaviour. Most patients reach a maximum dose of 750 mg daily, divided unevenly into two doses. This can be achieved by starting with 250 mg daily for 2 days, followed by 250-mg increments over 2-day intervals.

IX. Macrolides: Newer macrolides are used to treat atypical mycobacterial infection & cases with relapse.

1.6 Directly observed Treatment, Short Course (DOTS) Chemotherapy:

Directly observed therapy (DOT), which requires TB patients to take medicine under the direct observation of health workers or family members, was the key element of the DOTS strategy recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) and was shown effective in improving adherence to anti-TB treatment [23, 24]

Table 1: Treatment categories & sputum examination schedule in DOTS chemotherapy in India^[19]

TREATMENT REGIMEN			SPUTUM EXAMINATION			
Category of treatment	Type of patient	Regimen	Pretreatment sputum	Test at month	If result is	→THEN
New cases Category I	New sputum smear positive new sputum smear negative new extra-pulmonary** new others	2(HRZE)3 + 4(HR)3	+	2	-	Start continuation phase, test sputum again at 4 and 6 months#
					+	Continue intensive phase for one more month# Complete the treatment in 7months.
Previously treated Category II	Sputum smear-positive Relapse*** Sputum smear-positive Failure*** Sputum smear-positive treatment after default others	2(HRZES)3 + 1(HRZE)3 + 5(HRE)3	+	3	-	Start cont. phase, test sputum again at 5months 6months, completion of treatment
					+	Continue intensive phase for 1 month, test sputum again at 4months if sputum is +ve send sputum for culture and drug sensitivity as it might be MDR-TB#

*The no. before the letters refers to no. of months of treatment. The subscript after letters refers to no. of doses per week. H: Isoniazid (600mg), R: Rifampicin (450mg), Z: Pyrazinamide (1500mg), E: Ethambutol (1200mg), S: Streptomycin (750mg). Patients who weigh more than 60kg receive additional Rifampicin 150mg. patients more than 50 yrs old receive streptomycin 500mg. patients in categories I & II, who have a positive sputum smear at the end of the initial intensive phase receive an additional month of intensive phase treatment.

**Examples of seriously ill extra pulmonary TB cases are meningitis, disseminated TB, tuberculous pericarditis, peritonitis, bilateral or extensive pleurisy, spinal TB with neurological complications & intestinal & genito-urinary TB.

***In rare & exceptional cases, patients who are sputum smear-negative or who have extra-pulmonary can have relapse or failure. This diagnosis in all such cases should always be made by an MO & should be supported by culture or histological evidence of current, active tuberculosis. In these cases, the patient should be categorised as 'Other' and category II treatment.

#Any patient treated with Category I who has a positive smear at 5months of treatment should be considered a Failure & started on category II treatment, afresh. If category I sputum smear -ve case fails to improve or if patient develops pulmonary signs & positive smear at the end of intensive phase, it is considered treatment failure. Start category II treatment & confirm failure by culture & perform DST.

Daily administered non DOTS regime is followed in exceptional cases when there is adverse reaction to drugs used in short-course chemotherapy or when the patient cannot comply with regime. Treatment is given as follows:

1. Non- DOTS regime 1 (ND1): For new smear positive pulmonary seriously ill patients & extra pulmonary seriously ill patients -2 (SHE) +10 (HE)
2. Non- DOTS regime 2 (ND2): For smear negative not seriously ill patients & extra pulmonary not seriously ill patients-12 (HE)[23]

Category IV (DOTS-PLUS) treatment for MDR-TB [19]:

RNTCP has developed national guidelines based on WHO recommended international DOTS-Plus guidelines. As per guidelines, the diagnosis of MDR-TB is at the Intermediate Reference laboratories accredited to perform culture & drug sensitivity testing (DST). After diagnosis the treatment is initiated at designated DOTS-Plus sites.

Treatment regime: treatment used is -6 (9) Km Ofx Eto Cs ZE+ 18Ofx Eto CsE

(Km- kanamycin; Ofx- ofloxacin; Eto- ethinamide; Cs-cycloserine; Z- Pyrazinamide; E- ethambutol)

Duration of treatment: at least 6 months of intensive phase should be given extended upto 9 months in patients who have a positive culture result at fourth month of treatment. Minimum 18 months of continuation phase should be given following the intensive phase.

Category V for XDR-TB:

Standardized treatment regimen for XDR-TB under daily DOTS includes Capreomycin, PAS, Moxifloxacin, Clofazimine, Linezolid, and Amoxicillin/clavulanate for 6-12 months as intensive phase & PAS, Moxifloxacin high dose, Isoniazid, Clofazimine, Linezolid, Amoxicillin/clavulanate for 18months as a continuation phase. Clarithromycin &

Thiacetazone are used as a substitute drug in case of intolerance.

1.7 Prevention:

BCG VACCINATION [19]

Calmette and Guerin two French scientists began attenuating a virulent strain of *M. bovis* in 1906, with a view to develop a vaccine against tuberculosis. After 230 subcultures over a period of 13 years, they were able to evolve a strain – known as bacilli Calmette Guerin or BCG – which was a virulent for man while retaining its capacity to induce an immune response.

1. VACCINE: It consists of living bacteria derived from an attenuated *bovine* strain of tubercle bacilli.
2. TYPES OF VACCINE: There are two types of BCG vaccine – the liquid (fresh) vaccine & the freeze-dried vaccine. Freeze-dried vaccine is a more stable preparation than liquid vaccine with vastly superior keeping qualities.
3. DOSAGE: For vaccination, usual strength is 0.1mg in 0.1ml volume [25]
4. ADMINISTRATION: The standard procedure recommended by WHO is to inject vaccine intradermally using a "Tuberculin" syringe. A satisfactory injection should produce a wheal of 5mm in diameter. Two to three weeks after a correct intradermal injection of a potent vaccine, a papule develops at the site of vaccination. It increases slowly in about 5weeks. It then subsides or breaks into a shallow ulcer. Healing occurs spontaneously within 6 to 8 weeks leaving a permanent, tiny, round scar, typically 4-8 mm in diameter. This is normal reaction. [26]
5. AGE: In countries where tuberculosis is prevalent, national policy is to administer BCG very early in infancy either at birth or at 6 weeks of age simultaneously with other immunising

agents such as DPT & polio. In low prevalence countries BCG vaccination is given to high risk groups for e.g. Hospital personnel & tuberculin – negative contacts of known cases of TB particularly MDR-TB. [27, 28]

6. **PROTECTIVE VALUE:** The duration of protection is from 15 to 20 years.
7. **REVACCINATION:** After the development of the vaccine, it is not known whether booster doses are indicated or advisable [29]. In fact, BCG revaccination has not been included in the official immunization schedule under the expanded programme on immunization. Others recommend vaccination at school age irrespective of vaccination at birth, to prevent adult type of tuberculosis. [26]
8. **CONTRAINDICATIONS:** BCG should not be given to patients suffering from generalized eczema, infective dermatosis, hypogammaglobinaemia, to those with a history of deficient immunity (symptomatic HIV infection known or suspected congenital immunodeficiency, leukaemia, lymphoma or generalised malignant diseases). Patients under immunosuppressive treatment (corticosteroids, alkylating agents, antimetabolites, radiation), & in pregnancy.

1.8 Drug Resistance: All drugs used in the treatment of tuberculosis tend to produce resistant strains. It includes primary and secondary resistance. It develops due to incorrect prescription, irregular supply of drugs and noncompliance of treatment [19]

Multidrug-Resistant TB (MDR TB): Multidrug-resistant TB (MDR TB) is caused by TB bacteria that are resistant to at least isoniazid and rifampin, the two most potent TB drugs. It is estimated that primary MDR-TB in India is around 2.1%. The drug resistance in retreatment cases is 13-17%.

Extensively Drug-resistant TB (XDR TB): Extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR TB) is a rare type of MDR TB that is resistant to isoniazid and rifampin, plus any fluoroquinolone and at least one of three injectable second-line drugs (i.e., Amikacin, kanamycin, or Capreomycin). XDR-TB infections are very difficult to treat and characterized by high mortality.

1.9 Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme (RNTCP): [30]

Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme (RNTCP) formulated, adopted the internationally recommended Directly Observed Treatment Short-

course (DOTS) strategy, as the most systematic & cost effective approach to revitalize the TB control programme in India.

The objectives of RNTCP are:

1. Achievement of at least 85% cure rate of infectious cases of tuberculosis; through DOTS involving peripheral health functionaries; &
2. Augmentation of case finding activities through quality sputum microscopy to detect atleast 70% of estimated cases.

DOTS strategy adopted by RNTCP initially had 5 main components:

1. Political will & administrative commitment.
2. Diagnosis by quality assured sputum smear microscopy.
3. Adequate supply of quality assured short course chemotherapy drugs.
4. Directly observed treatment.
5. Systematic monitoring & accountability.

The WHO has set International Standards for Tuberculosis Care. These standards are intended to facilitate the effective engagement of all care-providers in delivering high-quality care for patients of all ages, including those with smear positive, smear negative, extra pulmonary tuberculosis, drug resistant tuberculosis, & tuberculosis combined with HIV infection. There are 6 standards for diagnosis, 9 standards for treatment & 2 standards for public health responsibilities. [31]

Stop TB Partnership targets[32]

By 2005: At least 70% of people with sputum smear positive TB will be diagnosed (i.e. under the DOTS strategy), & at least 85% cured.

By 2015: The global burden of TB will be reduced by 50% relative to 1990 levels. This means reducing the prevalence to 150 per 100,000 or lower & deaths to 15 per 100 000 per year or lower by 2015.

By 2050: The global incidence of TB disease will be less than or equal to 1 case per million population per year.

Components of stop TB strategy are as follows:

1. Pursuing high quality DOTS expansion & enhancement.
2. Addressing TB/HIV, MDR-TB & other challenges.
3. Contributing to health system strengthening.
4. Engaging all care-providers
5. Empowering people with TB, & communities. Enabling & promoting research.

Figure-6 Diagnosis of tuberculosis in RNTCP [30]

Initiation of treatment under RNTCP [30]

Under RNTCP case finding is passive. Patients presenting themselves with symptoms suspicious of tuberculosis are screened through 2 sputum smear examinations. Sputum microscopic examination is done in designated RNTCP microscopy centres. One sputum sample is not sufficient for diagnosis as the chance of detecting smear positive case is only 80%. Sputum microscopy not only confirms diagnosis, but also indicates the degree of infectivity & response to treatment.

The drugs are supplied in patient-wise boxes containing the full course of treatment, & packaged in blister packs. For the intensive phase, each blister pack contains one day's medication. For the continuation phase, each blister pack contains one week's supply of medication. The combi pack drugs for extension of intensive phase are supplied separately. The boxes are coloured according to the category of the regimen, red for category I, Blue for category II patients.

1.10 Programmatic Management of Drug Resistant TB: [30]

During 2009, some policy changes related to DOTS plus were made. The decisions taken were as follows:

1. The definition of the MDR suspect has been revised to include 'contacts of MDR cases who are

found to be smear positive' besides Cat I failures & Cat II patients who are smear positive at 4 months or later.

2. The existing exclusion criteria for MDR suspects i.e., age <15years & history of intake of second line drugs for more than one month in the past has been withdrawn. A new weight band (16-25 kgs) has been added for the treatment of the paediatric MDR patients;

3. In order to make the Cat IV regimen more effective it has been decided to replace Ofloxacin with Levofloxacin;

4. Guidelines for the management of MDR patients with pregnancy have been finalized. &

5. Guidelines for the management of XDR-TB patients with category V regimen have been formulated. Under RNTCP Phase II, it is planned to have a network of DOTS-Plus sites, as per international guidelines, capable of enrolling & providing care & management for upto 5,000 'new' multi-drug resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) cases a year.

1.11 National Strategic Plan (2012-2017): [30]

With progress in achieving objectives in the 11th Five Year Plan & defining newer targets of universal access to TB care, newer strategies have been developed as a comprehensive National Strategic

Plan under the 12th Five Year Plan. The following thrust areas were identified:

- Strengthening & improving the quality of basic DOTS services.
- Further strengthen & align with health system under NRHM.
- Deploying improved rapid diagnosis at the field level.
- Expand efforts to engage all care providers.

1.13 Achievements of RNTCP: [30]

The treatment success rate has more than trebled from 25% in 1998 to 88% in 2010. Death rate has been brought down seven folds from 29% to 4%. More than 15 million patients have been initiated in treatment, saving almost 2.5 million lives.

II- OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To determine whether the prescription is as per WHO standard drug regimen for TB management.
- Assess the adherence of the patients to prescribed drug regimen.
- Analyse the physicians prescribing pattern.
- To improve understanding of the relation of providers prescribing behaviour to ATT treatment guidelines may help to identify ways to improve development and timely communication of future treatment guidelines.
- To provide affective patient counselling to the patients.
- Identify common adverse effects resulting from CAT-I & CAT –II anti-TB drug regimen in patients.

III- METHODOLOGY:

An Observational and prospective study was performed in the Department of General Medicine

and outpatient TB centre, Osmania General Hospital for a period of 6 months with a sample size of 100 patients. Selection criteria includes patients above 12 years diagnosed with TB. Pediatric patients (<12yrs), pregnant and lactating women were excluded.

Plan of Work Procedure for Data Collection:

Based on the study objectives form was prepared - patient's socio-demographics, ATT adherence as well as ATT side effects information were made by taking into consideration all ATT medications which were prescribed by the physician to the patient. The proforma contained patient identification data, personal history, family history, risk factor details, Anti-tubercular treatment history, Anti-Tubercular treatment, laboratory investigations, ADR details & its assessment and patient follow-up details.

Essential laboratory investigation such as sputum test, Imaging such as (CT scan, MRI, chest X-ray etc.), Skin test i.e. Mantoux test and Blood tests.

Additional laboratory investigations like Hemoglobin, total blood cell count, serum creatinine, blood urea, serum bilirubin, SGPT, SGOT, Serum Albumin, PT time, INR, Blood sugar, Anti-HCV and data was also evaluated for patient demography, risk factors and type of ADR.

Treatment given to TB patients was correlated with standard WHO and RNTCP guidelines.

Cases of TB with pre-ATT, ATT and other drug therapy for co-infection were also documented.

Assessment of adherence:

In this study adherence was measured using self-reported data, attendance and pharmacy records.

The 8 question Morisky Medication Adherence scale (MMAS) with scores ranging from 1-13 was used to measure adherence behavior. Score > 11 indicates adherence to medication.

Figure-7 Morisky Medication Adherence scale (MMAS)

	YES	NO
1. Do you sometimes forget to take your medication?		
2. People sometimes miss taking their medications for reasons other than forgetting. Over the past 2 weeks, were there any days when you did not take your medication?		
3. Have you ever cut back or stopped taking your medication without telling your doctor because you felt worse when you took it?		
4. When you travel or leave home, do you sometimes forget to bring your medication?		
5. Did you take all your medication yesterday?		
6. When you feel like your symptoms are under control, do you sometimes stop taking your medication?		
7. Taking medication every day is a real inconvenience for some people. Do you ever feel hassled about sticking to your treatment plan?		
8. How often do you have difficulty remembering to take all your medication? Never/Rarely..... Once in a while..... Sometimes..... Usually..... All the time.....		
Adherence	MMAS-4 score	MMAS-8 score
High Adherence	0	0
Medium Adherence	1-2	1-2
Low Adherence	3-4	3-8

Table-2 MMAS Score

Assessment of patient knowledge:

A pre-determinant question was used to assess the patient's knowledge and medication adherence before after counselling. Patients were interviewed using pre-designed, pre-tested questionnaire. It has four domain i.e. physical health psychological health, social relationships and environment.

Table-3 Questions used to assess patients knowledge

S.NO	QUESTIONS
1.	Through smoking
2.	Through irregular diet
3.	Handshakes with TB patients
4.	Inhalation of droplets of nuclei in air generated by TB pts through coughing
5.	Eating from same plate
6.	Consequences of not treating TB
7.	Is TB curable
8.	Course of treatment
9.	DOTS therapy

Statistical analysis:

Analysis of data is done to inspect, transfer and model data with the goal of discovering useful information, suggesting conclusions and supporting decision making.

The information collected from the respondents were sorted, coded and entered in data sheet created in statistical package for social science (SPSS)

The descriptive statistical methods and statistical calculations were applied to analyze the data: Percentage, Arithmetic mean (average value) of the number of patients showing adherent and non-adherent behavior.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS for windows.

IV- RESULTS:

Analysis of Prescription Given for TB Management: All patients diagnosed with TB i.e. both pulmonary TB & Extra pulmonary TB receiving ANTI TUBERCULAR DRUGS. All the prescription was found to be as per WHO standard drug regimen for TB management. Patients were either receiving DOTS regimen including Category I or Category II and also AKT4 kit, Forecox, 4FDC.

Figure-8 Distribution of patients as per age

- The present study had predominance in age group of 40-49 yrs over other age groups.

Figure-9 Distribution of Patients Based On Gender

Among the subjects studied 70% were male subjects and 30% were female subjects.

Table-4 Distribution of Patients as Per Risk Factors

RISK FACTORS	% OF MALES	% OF FEMALES	TOTAL%
Smoking	33%	6%	40%
Tobacco chewing	11%	2%	15%
Alcohol	44%	5%	50%

- Risk factor which is more predominant in tertiary care teaching hospital is Alcohol consumption of 50% over smoking 40% and Tobacco chewing 15%.

Figure-10 Percentage of Symptoms Involved In Study

- Majority symptoms were SOB and fever i.e. (59% & 54%) respectively. Followed by cough more than 3 weeks with productive cough (51% & 34%) respectively.

Table-5 Distribution of Patients Based On Diagnosis

	No. of Patients	% of Patients
Newly diagnosed TB	54	54%
Known case of TB	46	46%

- In total of 100 patients known cases were 46% and newly diagnosed 54%.

Figure-11 Percentage of known TB & Newly diagnosed TB patients

Table-6 Percentage of Known TB Patients & Newly Diagnosed Based On Diagnosis

DIAGNOSIS	KNOWN CASE OF TB		NEWLY DIAGNOSED CASES	
	No. of Pts	% of Pts	No. of Pts	% of Pts
Sputum test for AFB +ve	19	19%	13	13%
CT scan (Chest/Brain/ABD)	26	26%	34	34%
CHEST X-RAY	9	9%	12	12%
USG abdomen	10	10%	9	9%
Adenosine Deaminases(ADA)	1	1%	12	12%
MRI -(brain/spine)	0	0	5	5%

- In study majority of cases were confirmed by CT scan (known 26% and new 34%) followed by Sputum test positive (known 19% & new 13%) and others test such as Chest x-ray, USG Abdomen and MRI.

Figure-12 Percentage of Patients Based On Site of Organ

- Patient were distributed based on site of organ in which majority of patients were of Pulmonary TB (75%) in comparison with extra pulmonary TB.
- In extra pulmonary TB majority of patients were of Pleural effusion (12%) and others were TB meningitis (10%), TB Spine (2%) and TB Abdomen (11%), and neurotuberculosis (1%).

Table-7 Distribution of Patients as Per Drug Regimen

SITE OF DISEASE	CAT I	CAT II	AKT4	FORECOX	4FDC
Pulmonary TB	56%	16%	1%	10%	5%
Extra pulm TB	25%	6%	2%	9%	1%
TOTAL	81%	22%	3%	19%	6%

- In the study, majority of patients were given Category I regimen [81%] in which patients of PTB receiving Category I were 56% & Extra pulmonary TB 25% followed by Category II regimen [22%] in which PTB were 16% & Extra pulmonary TB 6%
- Some patients receiving other drug regimen such as 3% AKT4, 19% Forecox & 4FDC- 6%.

Percentage of Co-Morbidities Observed In Tb Patients With Respect To Gender

In present study, TB condition most of the time co-existed with DM [20%] followed by LRTI & HTN [15%] COPD with Corpulmonale & Epilepsy [10%] & RVD [10%] & other comorbidities associated were Asthma, Anaemia, Epilepsy, CAD, Pneumonia. In present study, in all comorbidities males were predominant.

S.No	Type of Comorbidities	% of Co-MORBIDITIES		Total percentage
		MALES	FEMALES	
1.	LRTI	13%	2%	15%
2.	RVD	8%	2%	10%
3.	HTN	11%	4%	14%
4.	DM	14%	6%	17%
5.	Ascites	3%	2%	5%
6.	Asthma	1%	2%	3%
7.	CVA	3%	2%	5%
8.	CAD-ACS	7%	3%	10%
9.	Anemia	3%	1%	4%
10.	Epilepsy	8%	2%	10%
11.	COPD & Corpulmonale	10%	0	10%
12.	Liver diseases	4%	1%	5%

Table-8 Percentage of Co-Morbidities With Respect To Gender**Duration of Patient's Stay in Hospital:**

Out of 100 patients, most of the patients stayed in tertiary care teaching hospital for <10 days i.e. 61% in which

males [46%] & females [15%] in comparison with patient's stay >10 days i.e. 39% [males (26%) & female (13%)].

Figure-13 Duration of Patient's Stay in Hospital

Table-9 Effect of Patient Counselling On Knowledge Assessment about Modes of Transmission, On Disease & Treatment

Questions	% of patients having knowledge	
	Pre- counselling	Post- counselling
1. Through smoking	24.3%	41.4%
2. Through irregular diet	9.7%	36.5%
3. Handshakes with TB patients	21.2%	12.1%
4. Inhalation of droplets of nuclei in air generated by TB pts through coughing	29.2%	48.7%
5. Eating from same plate	17.0%	9.7%
6. Consequences of not treating TB	32.5%	48.7%
7. Is TB curable	19.2%	45.0%
8. Course of treatment	26.3%	43.6%
9. DOTS therapy	12.5%	26.7%

Percentage of Patient Adhering To Medication Regimen:

A Total of 100 Patients was included in study; The MMAS Adherence Questionnaire of every patient was used for Data Collection. In the MMAS scale, the no. of Patients who were Adherent to the Treatment was 72 Patients having summary score of > 11 i.e. Adherent & with Low Adherence were 28 patients with 5-8 Score. The range of summary score was from 5-13 with Mean Summary Score of 11.

Table-10 Percentage of patients adhering to Drug regimen

S.No	MMAS Adherence scale	MMAS score	No. of patients	% of patients
1.	Low Adherence	5-9	28	28%
2.	Adherence	11-13	72	72%

Table-11 Assessment of Morisky medication adherence scale

S.No	Questions	% of patients
1.	Ever forget to take medicine?	34%
2.	Miss medication for reason other than forgetting, over the past 2 weeks?	11%
3.	Have cut back medicine without doctor's knowledge?	14%
4.	Have forgotten medicine while travelling?	9%
5.	Missed medicine previous day?	3%
6.	When feel like symptoms under control do sometime stop taking medicine?	31%
7.	Feel hassled about sticking to treatment?	36%
8.	Difficulty in remembering treatment	
	Never	66%
	Rarely	10%
	Once in a while	13%
	Sometimes	5%
	Usually	6%
	All the time	0

Observation of patients responses on individual patients in MMAS scale, suggested that 34% of the respondents confessed to have sometimes forgotten medications. Patients [9%] had not taken medication while they were travelling, 14 patients [14%] stopped medications without telling the doctor, 31 patients [31%] did not take medication because they felt better & thought that disease was under control, while 36 patients [36%] felt hassled about sticking to treatment.

Figure-14 Distribution of Patients Based On ADE (Adverse Drug Event)

Among 100 TB patients, 75 patients i.e. 75% were associated with out adverse drug event (ADE) were as 25 patients i.e. 25% were associated with ADE.

Table-12 percentage of type of ADE (Adverse Drug Event) Monitored

Types of Adverse drug event	% of patients
Nausea	24%
Vomiting	25%
Itching	4%
Abdominal pain	14%
Joint pain	8%
Anemia	7%
Hepatotoxicity	10%
Neurotoxicity	2%

In 25% Patients associated with ADE, GIT reactions such as nausea & vomiting were seen in [(24%) & (25%) resp.] & Abdominal pain in [14% patients]. Skin conditions such as itching with rashes in 4 patients i.e.4%. Hepatotoxicity was also seen in 10 patients i.e. 10% based on Liver Function tests & Anaemia in 7% patients and Neurotoxicity in 2 patients i.e. 2%.

V-DISCUSSION:

TB is a serious public health issue causing immense morbidity, and distress not only to individuals but also to communities. It kills more adults in our country than any other infectious disease. [33]

In this study the disease incidence picks at the most economically age group of 10-80 years. Age play an important role in affecting the TB, even though middle age adults having a good immune power, the affecting rate of TB is very high with middle age

group of people only, the reason might be bad habits such as, cigarette smoking, tobacco chewing and alcoholism etc. In the present study it is seen that the more numbers of patients suffering from TB were in the age group of 40-49, 24 (24%), followed by 50-59,16 (16%) these statistic are comparable to previous study **Kasisrinivas et al. (2013)**[34] in which 26-35 Yrs. 13 (28.89%) and 36-45Yrs 12 (26.67%).

Among the study population the affecting rate of TB was more in males compare to females, reason might be life style, sex, often exposure to susceptible area and bad habits etc., these finding are well supported by previous finding of **Kasisrinivas et al.** [34]

In present study tuberculosis is encountered with HTN and DM, where in all the co-morbidities males were the predominant, which is deviating to a study conducted by **Deewan et al. (2010)** [35] and **Kumar et al. (2013)** [36]. In which tuberculosis was present with RVD & anemia as comorbidity.

Two types of therapy namely DOTs and general anti-TB drugs therapy was practiced in the present study, duration of therapy with anti-TB drugs were less medication adherence may be due to low economic status and poor intention towards the health maintenance. In DOTs therapy medication adherence was high and successful and culture sensitivity test was negative which improves the patient compliance. Unsuccessful treatment not only encourages the mortality but also increases further health and economic burden to the community. One of the reasons for unsuccessful treatment is the non-adherence. Poor adherence towards the drug therapy is the most common cause of initial treatment failure and reversion of disease in tuberculosis worldwide. However there are different methods for the assessment adherence. Among the methods most widely used, collection of urine samples at 0, 1, 2, 4 & 6 months of the study and has showed that compliance rates are higher at the first month compared to the second, fourth, six months **Khalili et al. (2008)** [37].

The study shows a slight increase of medication adherence rate, these shows that the patients aware of the need of treatment compliance. Pre determinant questions were used to assess medication adherence and the patient's knowledge before and after counselling. The patients Knowledge on causes and symptoms, modes of transmission, complication, and measures to prevent the spreading of the infection were assessed. There is a significant difference observed in this parameter on data of pre and post counselling. The same questions were also been used by **Tasmin et al. (2012)** [38], shows Knowledge about cause and treatment of tuberculosis among TB patients was quite good, however, misconceptions also exist.

We selected the MMAS scale (Morisky medication adherence scale) as this considers the impact of medication adherence to result in successful treatment. In this study to measure the impact of

counselling, the mean scores before and after counselling was found to be significantly different.

In Present Study, 75 patients i.e. 75% were associated with out adverse drug event (ADE) were as 25 patients i.e. 25% were associated with ADE. Adverse Drug Event reported were mild which includes nausea, vomiting (25%), and abdominal pain (14%). A study by **Sivaraj et al. (2008)** [39], RNTCP regimens with and without DOTS, also reported the majority of reactions to be mild (68.97%).

Major Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) were reported as Hepatotoxicity was seen in 10 % patients. Anaemia in 7% patients and Neurotoxicity in 2% patients.

Tuberculosis may be concomitant with other diseases, thus increasing the number of drugs patients use and predisposing them toward adverse reactions. In the study sample, patients who used more than five drugs in the course of their treatment developed more ADRs. **Kishore et al. (2008)** [40], observed in India that nearly half the patients who developed ADRs were prescribed more than five drugs.

VI- CONCLUSION:

All the prescription was found to be as per WHO standard drug regimen for TB management. Tuberculosis was observed more in adults, predominantly males. The present study had predominance in adults (70%). Among the subjects studied 70% were male subjects and 30% were female subjects.

Major risk factor observed among patients was Alcohol consumption [50%] over smoking [40%] & tobacco chewing [15%];

Majority symptoms observed in patients were SOB and fever i.e. (59% & 54%) respectively. Followed with cough more than 3 weeks with productive cough (51% and 34%) respectively.

In this study Majority of patients were of Pulmonary TB (75%) in comparison with extra pulmonary TB. In extra pulmonary TB majority of patients were of Pleural effusion (12%) and others were TB meningitis (10%), TB Spine (2%) and TB Abdomen (11%), and neurotuberculosis (1%).

Newly diagnosed TB cases 54% were more than known cases 46%. Category I drug regimen was given to 81% of patients as majority of cases collected were new cases so first CAT-I are prescribed. & Category II drug regimen was given to 22% of patients. Some patients receiving other drug

regimen such as 3% AKT4, 19% Forecox & 4FDC - 6%. HTN & DM were most common comorbidity in TB patients. A significant difference was observed in knowledge assessment of patients on the data collected pre & post counselling.

Assessment of medication adherence is made by MMAS scale, were the no. of Patients who were Adherent to the Treatment was 72 Patients having summary score of > 11 i.e. Adherent & with Low Adherence were 28 patients with 5-8 Score.

In Present Study, 75 patients i.e. 75% were associated with out adverse drug event (ADE) were as 25 patients i.e. 25% were associated with ADE. Major Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) were reported as Hepatotoxicity was seen in 10 patients i.e. 10%, Anaemia in 7% patients and Neurotoxicity in 2 patients i.e. 2%.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We acknowledge the valuable support and encouragement extended to us by **Dr. Fakhruddin Mohammed**, Chairman, MESCO College of Pharmacy and **Dr. Mir Wajahath Ali**, Convener, MESCO College of Pharmacy, for providing us the opportunity to embark on this project. We also wish to express our heartfelt thanks to **Dr. V. H. Sastry**, Principal, MESCO College of Pharmacy, for providing necessary arrangements and support without which this work would not have attained this standard.

REFERENCES:

1. WHO (2011), *Global Tuberculosis Control, Surveillance, Planning Financing*, WHO Report 2011.
2. WHO (2012), *Tuberculosis Control in South-East Asia Region, Regional Report*, 2012.
3. Govt. Of India (2012), *TB India 2012, RNTCP Annual Status Report.*, DGHS, Ministry of Health & Family welfare, New Delhi.
4. World Health Organization (WHO). Global tuberculosis report 2015. Geneva. 2015. Available at: http://www.who.int/tb/publications/global_report/en/ Accessed 09 Jan 2016.
5. Govt of India (2010) TB India 2010, RNTCP Status Report, Central TB Division, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, New Delhi.
6. Bluhmberg HM, Burman WJ, Chaison RE, et al, American Thoracic Society CfDC, Prevention and the Infectious Diseases S American Thoracic Society CfDC and Prevention\ Infectious Diseases S America: treatment of tuberculosis, *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2003; 167: 603-662.
7. Borgdoeff MW, Floyd K, Broekmans JF,

Interventions to reduce tuberculosis mortality and transmission in low and middle-income countries. *Bull World organ* 2002; 80: 217-227.

8. Greinert U, Zabel P. Tuberculosis-current therapeutic principles, *Internist* 2003; 44: 1394-1405.
9. Cramin JM, Finkenflugel HJ, Moller V, Nieboer AP. TB treatment initiation and adherence in South African community influenced more by perceptions than by knowledge of tuberculosis; *BMC Public health*2010; 10: 72.
10. Kehede A, Wabe NT. Medication adherence and its determinants among patients on concomitant tuberculosis and antiretroviral therapy in South west Ethiopia, *N Am J Med Sci* 2012; 4: 67-71.
11. Lertmaharit S, Kamol-Ratankul P, Sawert H, Jittimane S, Wangmanee S. Factors associated with compliance among tuberculosis patients in Thailand, *J Med Assoc Thai* 2005; 88(Suppl 4);S149-156.
12. Mestini MM, Newell JN, Walkey JD, et al. Quality of tuberculosis care and its association with patient adherence to treatment in eight Ethiopian districts, *Health Policy Plan* 2009; 24:457-466.
13. Munro SA, Lewin SA, Smith HJ, Engel ME, Frethein A, Volmink J. Patient adherence to tuberculosis treatment: a systematic review of qualitative research. *PLoS Med* 2007; 4: e238.
14. Maartens G, Wilkinson RJ. Tuberculosis. *Lancet*. 2007; 370:2030-43. Doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(07)61262-8.
15. World Health Organization (WHO). DOTS. Geneva. 2015. Available at: <http://who.int/tb/dots/en/>. Accessed 23 Aug 2015.
16. Govt. Of India (2012), Notification of TB cases, Ministry of Health & Family welfare, New Delhi.
17. Available at: <http://www.healthcommunities.com/tuberculosis/types.shtml>
18. K.Park; Text book of Preventive & Social Medicine; Twenty second Edition; M/s Banarsidas Bhanot Publishers; 2013; Pg no: 171.
19. K.Park; Text book of Preventive & Social Medicine; Twenty second Edition; M/s Banarsidas Bhanot Publishers; 2013; Pg no: 171-182.
20. WHO (2010), *Policy framework for Implementing New Tuberculosis Diagnostics*, March 2010.
21. Joseph T. Dipiro, Robert L. Talbert, Gary C. Yee, Garu R. Matzke, Barbara G. Wells, L. Michael Posey; *Pharmacotherapy Handbook*; Eight Edition; McGraw Hill Professional; 2011; Page No. 1843-1850

22. American Thoracic Society, CDC, Infectious Diseases Society of America. Treatment of tuberculosis. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report: Recommendations and Reports, 2003, 52(RR-11):1–77.
23. Garrido Mda S, et al. Factors Associated with Tuberculosis Treatment Default in an Endemic Area of the Brazilian Amazon: A Case Control-Study. PLoS ONE. 2012; 7:e39134. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0039134.
24. Volmink J, Garner P. Directly observed therapy for treating tuberculosis. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2007; 4:CD003343
25. WHO (1964). *Techn. Rep. Ser.*, No. 651.
26. Dam, H.G.T. et al (1976) *Bull WHO*, 54 (3) 255.
27. Snell, N.J.C (1985). P.G. Doctor Middle East April 1985, 1232.
28. WHO (1964). *Techn. Rep. Ser.*, No. 652.
29. Eichenwald, H.F. (1983). In: Nelson Textbook of Paediatrics, 12th Edition, Saunders.
30. K.Park; Text book of Preventive & Social Medicine; Twenty second Edition; M/s Banarsidas Bhanot Publishers; 2013; Pg no: 394-399.
31. WHO: Weekly Epidemiological Record, No.5, dated 3rd Feb 2006.
32. WHO (2006), *Global Tuberculosis Control, Surveillance, Planning Financing*, WHO Report 2006.
33. Nasara Reddy et al; Studies on Medication Adherence and Quality of Life in Tuberculosis patients; International Journal of Pharmacy(2015)
34. Kasi Srinivas, SreeDevi. Studies on treatment outcome of new sputum smear positive tuberculosis patients among tribal population in Kurnool district. *Int. J Res Dev Health*. 2013; 1(1): 5-1
35. P K Dewan, D Gupta, B G Williams, R Thakur, D Bachani, A Khera et al. National estimate of HIV seroprevalence among tuberculosis patients in India . *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis*. 2010: 14(2): 247 – 49
36. Pravat Kumar Thatoi, Sagar Khadanga. Pulmonary Tuberculosis and its hematological correlates *Transw Med J*. 2013; 1(1): 11-13
37. Khalili H, Dashti-khavidaki S, and Sajadi S, Hajiabolbaghi M. *DARU* 2008: Vol.16: PP. 47-50.
38. SariaTasnim, AminurRahman and F. M. AnamulHoque. *Pulmonary Medicine*: 2012: Article ID 352850: 5 pages.
39. Sivaraj R, Umarani S, Parasuraman S, Muralidhar P. Revised National Tuberculosis Control Program regimens with and without directly observed treatment, short-course: A comparative study of therapeutic cure rate and adverse reactions. *Perspect Clin Res* 2014; 5(1):16-9.
40. Kishore PV, Subish P, Pradip O, Shankar PR. Pattern of Adverse Drug Reactions Experienced by Tuberculosis Patients in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Western Nepal. *Pak J Pharm Sci*. 2008; 21(1):51–6.